

Station, Kaohsiung, Taiwan, introduced through International Rice Testing Program nurseries in 1981, and further evaluated by the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice-Africa and in multilocal coordinated rice evaluation trials (CRET) in Nigeria. After 3 yr in CRET, the line was further evaluated in farmers' fields by the National Ac-

celerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP).

FARO 50 is a varietal name given to line ITA230. It was selected from the F₄ lines introduced from the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia. As line 6902, it was selected for yield potential and blast resistance at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan. The line was

evaluated in CRET and NAFPP prior to its release.

Both FARO 44 and FARO 50 are resistant to leaf blast and leaf scald, but are susceptible to iron toxicity, ARGM, and rice yellow mottle virus. They have long, slender grains and high amylose content. Both are popular in irrigated rice areas of north and central zones of Nigeria. ■

Xingxiangyou 77, a high-yielding and fine-quality semi-aromatic hybrid rice

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Xingxiangyou 77 was developed at HHRRC using aromatic cytoplasmic male sterile line Xiangxiang A and nonaromatic restorer line Minghui 77. It was extensively tested and approved for release to farmers by the Hunan Provincial Crop Variety Release Committee in February 1997. Xiangxiang A, improved from the first aromatic CMS line Xiangxiang 2A, is another aromatic

CMS line developed by HHRRC. The new line has stable male sterility and better outcrossing characteristics than Xiangxiang 2A. Minghui 77, developed by the Sanming Agricultural Institute, Fujian, China, is a popular strong restorer line with good grain quality. The cross between these two parents was first made in 1993. In 1994, the hybrid was tested in the Hunan Rice Variety Multilocal Trial and yielded 6.9 t ha⁻¹ on average at all five locations, 5.5% higher (significant at 5% level) than check Weiyou 64. In the same year, it gave a mean yield of 5.9 t ha⁻¹ at six locations in the trial of new commercial fine-quality rice varieties of Hunan Province with a yield advan-

tage of 2.9% over check Xiangwanxian 1. Tested in the Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trials of 1995 and 1996, it gave a mean grain yield of 6.8 t ha⁻¹ over 14 and 12 locations, respectively, with yields of 2.3% and 5.6% higher than those of check Weiyou 64 (Table 1). In the on-farm trials and demonstration plots, it generally yielded 6.8 to 7.7 t ha⁻¹ when grown as late rice in a double-cropping system.

Most of the variety's grain quality characters met the 2nd class standards of fine-quality rice issued by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (Table 2). Furthermore, because its CMS line Xingxiang A is aromatic and its restorer line Minghui 77 is nonaromatic,

Table 1. Agronomic characters of Xingxiangyou 77. Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trial, China.

Hybrid	Year	Locations (no.)	Hybrids tested (no.)	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)
Xingxiangyou 77	1995	14	10	114.0	99.1	108.7	69.2	27.4	6.8 ns
	1996	12	11	114.8	96.0	105.6	77.8	28.3	6.9 ns
Weiyou 64 (check)	1995	14	10	114.0	97.0	98.0	72.2	28.5	6.6
	1996	12	11	113.3	91.0	100.7	74.9	29.3	6.5

^ans = yields not significant by Duncan's SSR test (in 1995) or by Fisher's PLSD test (in 1996). The experiment used three replications.

Table 2. Grain quality performance of Xingxiangyou 77.

Hybrid/standard	Institutes ^a doing the testing (year)	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Kernel		Chalky		Gelatinization temperature (alkali value)	Gel consistency (mm)	Amylose content (%)	Protein content (%)
					Length (mm)	L/W	Rice (%)	Area (%)				
Xingxiangyou 77	CNRRRI (1995)	81.6	73.6	58.4	7.1	3.1	46	50	6.8	62	24.0	12.2
	HRRI (1995)	81.0	77.5	56.0	7.2	3.1	61	26				
	HRRI (1996)	81.0	66.8	61.0	7.1	3.0	58	26				
CMA standard	1st class	>81	>74	>59	6.5-7.5	>3.0	<5	<5	>4	>60	17-22	>8
	2nd class	>79	>72	>54	5.6-6.5	2.5-3.0	<10	<10	>4	41-60	<25	>8

^a CNRRRI: Chinese National Rice Research Institute; HRRI: Hunan Rice Research Institute; CMA: Chinese Ministry of Agriculture.

Xingxiangyou 77 is considered a semi-aromatic hybrid rice. It produces only partially aromatic grains on each plant (owing to F₂ segregation for aromatic genes). Consumers prefer semi-aromatic rice to pure aromatic rice.

Using the 1-9 scales of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, the hybrid scored 6 for leaf blast, 7 for neck blast, and 7 for bacterial leaf blight.

When planted as late rice in the double-cropping system in Hunan,

Xingxiangyou 77 matured in about 115 d (Table 1). It was about 98 cm tall with strong tillering ability. Its seed set was 75% with a mean of 105-110 spikelets panicle⁻¹ and a 1000-grain weight of 27-28 g. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

New rice varieties for the rainfed lowlands of Cambodia

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The rainfed lowland rice ecosystem is highly diverse in Cambodia. Several niches exist within the ecosystem, each of which may require different rice varieties of early, medium, or late maturity.

The Varietal Recommendations Committee (VRC) of the Cambodian Department of Agronomy approved the release of three modern, photo-period-insensitive, early-duration (less than 120 d) and three modern, photo-period-insensitive, medium-duration (120-150 d) varieties selected by CIAP between 1990 and 1993. In 1995, the VRC approved the release of six pureline selections from traditional Cambodian varieties for cultivation in the rainfed lowland ecosystem.

The six selections originated from the traditional varieties Pram Bei Kuor (PPD679), Sambak Kraham (PPD597), Sraem Choab Chan (Germplasm B-293), Changkom Ropeak (Germplasm 90B-528), Kantuy Touk (PPD156), and Sae Nang (Germplasm 90B-429). The VRC decided that all varieties released in Cambodia will be assigned continuous numbers following the letters CAR, which signify "Cambodia rice." So these selections were named CAR1-CAR6, respectively.

In the early 1970s, Cambodia's rice germplasm collections were sent to IRRI headquarters in the Philippines for safekeeping. Many of these varieties were subsequently lost in Cambodia

Table 1. Yield (t ha⁻¹) of photoperiod-sensitive, traditional medium- and late-duration rice varieties and checks^a for rainfed lowland ecosystem in Cambodia.

Year	Trial ^b	Medium-duration varieties				Late-duration varieties			
		CAR 1	CAR 2	CAR 3	MS	CAR 4	CAR 5	CAR 6	TS2
1990	PYT (0, 2)	-	-	-	-	4.2	3.3	3.9	3.4
1991	PYT (1, 3)	3.3	3.8	3.8	3.2	5.2	4.4	4.6	3.7
1992	AYT (9, 6)	3.0	3.3	3.3	2.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	3.9
1993	AYT (9, 8)	3.2	3.4	3.3	2.9	3.6	3.5	3.4	2.6
1994	AYT (6, 10)	3.0	3.1	3.3	2.6	3.7	3.4	3.6	2.8
	Mean	3.1	3.3	3.3	2.8	4.0	3.7	3.8	3.0
	% Increase over check	11	18	18	0	29	19	23	0

^aChecks for medium- and late-duration trials are Mahsuri (MS) and Toul Samrong 2 (TS2). ^bPYT = preliminary yield trial, AYT = advanced yield trial. The first and second values in parentheses refer to the number of locations involved in medium- and late-duration trials, respectively.

Table 2. Date of 50% flowering, growth duration, and plant height of photoperiod-sensitive, traditional medium- and late-duration varieties and checks. 1993-94 wet seasons. Cambodia.

Variety	Date of 50% flowering		Growth duration ^a (d)		Height ^a (cm) 1992-94
	1993	1994	1993	1994	
<i>Medium-duration</i>					
CAR1	4 Nov-3 Dec	13 Nov-1 Dec	160 (145-172)	166 (150-180)	127 (95-180)
CAR2	7 Nov-9 Dec	22 Oct-10 Dec	162 (146-178)	165 (150-182)	126 (90-178)
CAR3	1 Nov-3 Dec	7 Nov-26 Nov	156 (138-172)	162 (150-175)	122 (89-167)
MS	9 Oct-4 Dec	8 Oct-15 Nov	150 (128-170)	142 (135-151)	113 (81-156)
Sowing time	22 Jun-31 Jul	21 Jun-17 Jul	22 Jun-31 Jul	21 Jun-17 Jul	-
<i>Late-duration</i>					
CAR4	15 Nov-4 Dec	14 Nov-28 Nov	171 (162-182)	174 (160-186)	132 (93-161)
CAR5	17 Nov-10 Dec	16 Nov-1 Dec	173 (162-182)	177 (166-190)	134 (93-184)
CAR6	13 Nov-5 Dec	14 Nov-28 Nov	171 (161-183)	174 (161-187)	129 (94-183)
TS2	25 Nov-12 Dec	18 Nov-6 Dec	182 (171-195)	182 (169-196)	125 (96-194)
Sowing time	18 Jun-14 Jul	15 Jun-20 Jul	18 Jun-14 Jul	15 Jun-20 Jul	-

^aThe first value is the mean. Values in parentheses represent the range.

because of the lack of cold storage facilities and the civil unrest in the 1970s. In the 1980s, the collections were returned to Prey Phdau Station at the government's request. The source populations for CAR1, CAR2, and CAR5 belonged to these collections and could have been completely lost if they had not been conserved at IRRI's International Rice Genebank. The source populations for the other varieties released were part of the CIAP

germplasm collection obtained through the joint efforts of the Department of Agronomy, provincial agriculture offices, nongovernment organizations, and CIAP.

On the basis of preliminary yield trials (PYT) and advanced yield trials (AYT) conducted for several years at multiple locations, CAR1 yielded 11% more than the check Mahsuri while CAR2 and CAR3 yielded 18% more (Table 1). CAR4 has a yield advantage of